

Staffing practices in the private sector in Sri Lanka

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Abstract

Purpose- This paper presents and discusses the findings of a study of staffing practices in the Sri Lankan private sector with particular reference to junior level managerial jobs. The scope of staffing practices consisted of six major areas namely, the usage of information from job analysis in staffing, the sources of labour, selection criteria and selection methods in use, the validation of staffing practices and the involvement of HR managers and line managers in staffing.

Design/methodology/approach- Sixty two companies were selected based on stratified random sample method from two major types of companies -listed in stock exchange and non-listed. A self-administered questionnaire was chosen as the main mode for data collection. For the study, a combination of quantitative and qualitative inquiries was adopted.

Findings- Sri Lankan companies placed higher weightage to external labour market in the recruitment and use objective criteria in selection. The common ground for the companies is the heavy role that the interview, written examination, psychometric test and assessment centre play as selection methods.

Originality/value- The credibility of management concepts is partly determined by its diffusion across the world. Also, such credibility will be enhanced if the concepts are viewed to be applicable in different country contexts. However, staffing practices remains dubious due to lack of empirical studies in the Asian developing country context. Specifically, no such studies have been conducted in the context of Sri Lanka.

Keyword(s): Staffing; Recruitment; Selection; Human resource management; Line management; Sri Lanka.

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

Staffing, which is concerned with recruitment, selection, placement, evaluation and promotion of individuals lies at the heart of how businesses procure human resource (HR) in an organization (Peters *et al.*, 2000). In this regard, focus is on matching the capabilities and inclinations of prospective candidates against the demands and rewards inherent in a given job (Herriot, 1989; Montgomery, 1996; Plumbley, 1985, Zhu and Dowling, 2002). Much of the recent literature on human resource management (HRM) emphasised the importance of staffing (Plumbley, 1985;

Smith and Robertson, 1993; Tanova, 2003; Terpstra, 1996; Williamson, 2000). For instance, Plumbley (1985) suggests that the profitability and even the survival of an organization usually depends upon the calibre of the workforce and argued that the costs of ineffectual commercial viability could often be attributed to decades of ineffective staffing practices. Even in today's technically advanced business environment, human factor is instrumental to the success of an organization. Thus, it is argued that with the changes in the business climate and the rise of reengineering to meet the needs of organizations in the area of downsizing or cost diminution, organizations must equip to recruit individuals who can operate in non-structured or "virtual" organizations (Heraty and Morley, 1998). Though HR could be enhanced continuously through development, the first step towards making sure that employees possess the qualities sought for is to develop and institute appropriate staffing practices (Ahmad and Schroeder, 2002). In some service sectors such as software development, qualities reside more clearly with individual employees as opposed to within an organization and required qualities may change before an employer could develop these among its own employees (Heraty and Morley, 1998). Thus, staffing process of an organization is intended to identify prospective candidates who have at least some of the required qualities and attributes to fit well with the hiring organization. Further, effective staffing practices reduce labour turnover and enhance employee morale (Bonn and Forbringer, 1992; Lee et al., 1999). Hence staffing represents one of the key factors that influence the success of an organization (Judge and Ferris, 1994; Tanova, 2003; Williamson, 2000).

The focus of this paper is on the discussion of the results of an empirical investigation into staffing practices in Sri Lanka with reference to junior level managerial jobs. The paper

examines a number of specific questions. These include whether information from job analysis is used in staffing? What are the internal and external sources of labour and do different sources influence the nature of the pool of labour attracted? What selection criteria and selection methods are used? What measures are taken to validate staffing practices? and the extent to which HR managers and line managers involve in the staffing process? Though attention has been devoted to investigate staffing practices in the Western world, to date there remains a dearth of empirical research conducted to address these in the Asian developing country context. For two main reasons research into management practices of Asian developing countries, Sri Lanka in particular, is important. First and foremost, as the importance of staffing continues, important as it is to the future of the management discipline and the profession is to address to what extent staffing practices are echoed in the Asian developing countries. This is important as the credibility of management concepts is partly determined by its diffusion across the world. Thus, it is essential to study staffing practices in different socio-cultural settings; the credibility will be enhanced if the concepts are viewed to be applicable in different country contexts. However, staffing practices in the Asian context remains dubious due to lack of empirical studies. Specifically, no such studies have been conducted in the context of Sri Lanka. Thus, from a theoretical perspective, it is essential to increase the understanding of this topic; this could stimulate further research in this area. Second, despite tumultuous internal struggles, the Sri Lankan economy has shown resilience and has forged ahead showing a satisfactory rate of growth, which could be attributed to increase in foreign direct investments (FDI). Low wages are unimportant if labour is unproductive or its productivity is hampered by negative attitudes towards work. The productivity of Sri Lankan labour has been rated as the second highest in Asia (Rasaputram, 2001). Thus, from a practical standpoint it is vital to provide practitioners

with key information that could enable them to make informed managerial decisions in a non-western work environment. This is one of the most important contributions to literature to reveal staffing practices of a developing country destined for FDI. In this context, the paper presents an account of staffing practices in the Sri Lankan organizations, which is potentially important for scholars and practitioners alike. For the investigation, a survey was conducted in 62 companies belong to two major types of companies (*listed in stock exchange and non-listed*) in 2005 based on the assumption that there might be significant differences between listed and non-listed companies in their staffing practices. The conclusions address existing practice and implications.

Review of literature

Use of job analysis information in staffing

There is a need to ensure that staffing practices adopted by an organization is coherent and consistent with its business strategies and with other associated functions of HRM such as human resource development, and pay and benefits. When comparing the relative importance of different stages and activities of the staffing process, job analysis is identified as the *sine qua non* for virtually all HR planning, development, and utilization activities carried out by organizations (Stewart and Carson 1997). Job analysis information plays a major role in staffing as it provides a clear indication of particular requirements of the job, where that job fits into the overall organization structure, and a description of the kind of person who should be hired for the job. Thus, traditionally staffing is accomplished by developing concise definitions of necessary technical requirements (job analysis) and then by determining which job applicants possess the

specific knowledge, skills and abilities needed to successfully fulfil those requirements. The role of each individual is prescribed in relation to the goal of the organization or company policy dictates the entire staffing process. From this perspective, staffing is accomplished by rationally choosing applicants who possess the technical qualifications best suited for performing a narrow scope of clearly defined duties (Stewart and Carson 1997).

When the world of work is undergoing changes, the types of jobs needed also tend to change. According to Stewart and Carson (1997), modern organizations are moving beyond hierarchical structures and controls toward flexible, network oriented, team based designs. Hence, the contemporary organizing perspective assumes that work activities are structured around people, and that a person's role is largely dependent on the particular contracts individual enters (Stewart and Carson 1997). The trend toward relational organizing should thus be accomplished by reduced reliance on the results of objective job analysis. These fundamental changes in the nature of work create many problems and questions (Peterson et al 2001). In this context, Stewart and Carson (1997) stated that while the legal environment currently implies businesses to conduct some type of job analysis, the degree to which participants agree about and actually follow job analysis depend on the extent to which the structure is based on evolved relationships rather than hierarchical relationships. Thus, staffing is one particular facet of contemporary organizations that is in need of a new perspective. Yet, staffing needs to be considered as an integrated process rather than a marginal, ad hoc activity (Hsu and Leat, 2000). In this context, job analysis as a part of the staffing process is an understudy area.

Selection criteria

Organizations concentrate on prospective employees' "hard" technical skills and also their "soft" behavioural skills. However, it was argued that most often organizations' recruitment and selection processes emphasise prospective employees' "hard" skills and focus very little on their "soft" skills (Ahmad and Schroeder, 2002). Though employees can generally be trained in tools and techniques within a shorter time period, the development of soft skills requires relatively longer time period. Evidence suggests that effective communication, leadership, motivation, analytical skills, and organizational ability were among important qualities that were sought for during the selection process (Ahmad and Schroeder, 2002; Stewart and Knowles, 2000; Zhu and Dowling, 2002). Evidence also suggests that organizations pay increasing interest on innovative and multi-experienced personnel (Heraty and Morley, 1998). However, the weightage given to the desired qualities could vary by the nature of the job to be performed. For instance, the importance of self motivated personnel increases if individuals were expected to show their ability in terms of working unsupervised, generating their own work and meeting deadlines rather than expecting always to be given a task. Though it is advantageous to have selection criteria for jobs to be documented, research evidence reveals that the majority of organizations do not maintain well-documented selection criteria (Stewart and Knowles, 2000). When organizations do not have selection criteria documented, they have to rely upon the interviewer retrieving information purely from memory without making reference to documentation during selection interviews (Stewart and Knowles, 2000).

Selection methods

Selection methods available for organizations can be characterised along a continuum that ranges from more traditional methods of interviews, application forms and references, through to more sophisticated techniques that encapsulate aptitude tests, assessment centres, work samples, psychological testing, and so forth. The degree to which a selection technique is perceived as effective and perhaps sophisticated is determined by its reliability and validity (Hunter and Hunter, 1984; Muchinski, 1986; Salgado *et al.*, 2001; Terpstra, 1996). Evidence also reveals that the choice of selection methods is inherently linked to the job category in question. Curriculum vitae (CVs) and cover letters are used to shortlist candidates for interviews (Stewart and Knowles, 2000). However, it is widely held that application form as a discrete selection tool is open to misinterpretation, particularly where applicants portray a false persona (Muchinski, 1986). Evidence further reveals the wide use of presentations and reference checks as selection devices (Stewart and Knowles, 2000; Heraty and Morley, 1998; Robertson and Makin, 1986; Zottoli, 2000). However, it has been shown that referees who like a particular candidate tend to write longer and more complimentary references (Dobson, 1989; Reilly and Chao, 1982). As a selection method, organizations perceive interviews to be the easiest, quickest and cheapest method (Stewart and Knowles, 2000). Some organizations tend to use series of interviews to clarify whether the candidate possesses the qualities he/she mentioned in the application or CV and also to assess whether he/she is the right person. Evidence reveals the use of scoring systems during the interviews when more than one person assesses candidates. However, organizations do not always solely depend upon the interview performance; use tests to support the interview (Stewart and Knowles, 2000). The reason for the use of psychometric tests is to measure

psychological traits that are considered to be relevant to the performance of job tasks (Van Clieaf, 1991). A test score banding method, in which selection within bands takes into account criteria that are likely to enhance workforce diversity, has also been proposed by Campion et al (2001). Assessment centres are formal, multi-day sessions in which candidates are tested on their skills relative to the job for which they applied for (Sackett 1987, Van Clieaf, 1991, Campbell and Bray, 1993). Though sophisticated selection techniques such as assessment centres and psychometric tests are reported to be used in a piece-meal, incremental basis rather than as a norm for all job vacancies, it appears that these methods would become more popular (Heraty and Morley, 1998).

Problems in staffing

It is argued that mistakes are caused by the fact that organizations generally give little thought to the critical nature of the staffing decisions and involve little or no attempt to validate staffing practices (Florkowski and Schuler, 1994; Ifill and Moreland 1999). Evidence reveals that HR managers tend to rely on feedback from line managers on probationary period and disciplinary procedures to weed out mistakes; no attempt is made to analyse the constitution of labour turnover. Thus, organizations are surprised and disappointed when an appointment fails, and often the person appointed is blamed rather than recognising the weaknesses in the process and methodology. Ifill and Moreland (1999) identified 11 main areas where the recruitment and selection process of an organization fails. Some of these areas include no obvious link of recruitment and selection with HR strategy and with broader organizational goals, unavailability of job analysis information, the use of invalid prediction methods, the lack of monitoring of the

recruitment and selection process, and the lack of remedial actions in those organizations that do monitor staffing practices. In this context, the need of investigating new hires' and applicants' reactions to selection methods and the decision-making in the selection process have been highlighted (Anderson *et al.*, 2001; Bauer et al, 2001; Bauer et al, 1998; Blackman, 2006; Bernerth, 2005; Reeve et al, 2006; Truxillo et al, 2006). Further, Ryan et al (2005) and Jones et al (2006) also revealed the importance of investigating into how recruitment source (referral, newspaper ad) affects post hire outcomes such as turnover and performance while Anderson and Goltsi (2006) revealed the importance of investigating into psychological effects of selection methods. Furthermore, Slaughter et al (2005) highlighted the importance of comparing profiles of an organization's pool of new hires to those of the larger applicant population. Thus, HR specialists have an important role to be played in connection to assessing staffing practices. However, the non-existence of trained HR managers was acknowledged as a potential problem for the absence of formal systems for the validation of staffing practices (Jameson, 2000; Stewart and Knowles, 2000).

Involvement of HR and line managers in staffing

HRM literature gives evidence to growing tendency towards decentralisation and a concomitant shift towards greater devolvement of responsibility to line management (Carroll, 1991; Kamoche, 1994; Storey, 1995). In the process of decentralisation, there is a substantial sharing of decision-making of HR activities with line management- sharing in the sense of being a product of consultation between the HR department and line management than it was solely with either HR specialist or line management. In the main, primary responsibility remains with the HR

department but line management appeared to have more devolved responsibility. The new role of HR specialists has become supporting and facilitating line management in these tasks, not to control them (Hsu and Leat, 2000). Thus, it could be argued that line management involvement in the areas traditionally held to be the domain of HR specialists is becoming more pervasive (Heraty and Morley, 1998). Staffing is no exception. It is completed through a combination of HR specialist and line management involvement (Heraty and Morley 1998; Zhu and Dowling, 2002). It was believed that by allowing line managers to select candidates for positions in respective departments could help achieve a better fit between the job and the candidates (Zhu and Dowling, 2002). Further, evidence reveals that line management played a considerably greater role in the final selection decisions than that was indicated for the staffing process as a whole (Hsu and Leat, 2000).

Economic and social environment in Sri Lanka

Democratic Socialist Republic of Sri Lanka is an island in the Indian Ocean at the base of the Indian Sub-Continent. Sri Lanka has been under Portuguese, Dutch and British rule since 1505 and became independent in 1948. At the time of regaining independence, the production of and trade in plantation crops contributed to a major share of the national income; the economy was open to free trade (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). Though from mid 1960s the governments gradually introduced an array of controls in 1977 far-reaching policy reforms had been introduced to free the economy from the controls (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). A major boost to employment generation from early 1980s came mainly from the expansion of local private sector and foreign investments stimulated by the liberalised economic policies (Central

Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). Employment in manufacturing and service sectors increased (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998). The importance of public sector as a major source for providing employment opportunities declined since 1991 (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 1998).

The quality of manpower of a country is influenced by the level of access to education. As a result of the free education policy for all citizens of the country from primary education to the graduation, since 1945, the majority of new entrants to the Sri Lankan labour force endowed with primary and secondary education (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2004). However, employment creation for the growing educated labour force has been a problem confronted by successive governments since independence. Unemployment read as 9 per cent in 2002 (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2004). The most alarming feature of the unemployment problem in Sri Lanka has been its skewness towards young, first time job seekers. The unemployment rate is at the highest among youth in the age group of 15-29 years. Further, unemployment indicates an increasing trend with the increase in the level of education (Central Bank of Sri Lanka, 2004).

However, the scarcity of research in the Sri Lankan organizations on staffing practices limits the ability to provide guidance on one hand to those who seek employment opportunities. On the other, for investors, to make informed managerial decisions in a non-western work environment.

Methodology

Sample

The research is designed to compare staffing practices between two major types of companies (*listed in stock exchange and non-listed*). Literature reveals that where there is a separation of

functions between owners and managers in publicly held corporations, there is a potential conflict of interests (Barber and Manger, 1997). By contrast, where the owners are also the managers, this potential source of conflict is avoided. This gives a non-listed company the advantage over a publicly-listed corporation in that ownership is focused and intense. The manager-owner combination is a powerful force and for outside providers of finance it can sometimes be too powerful. Without separation of power, the managerial role dominates the sobering influence of the shareholder. The managerial ego dominates that of traditional accounting control, meaning the manager determines the resource allocation process, including staffing for their organizations. On the other hand, listed companies may have a greater tendency to recruit internally, across all managerial grades, than do their non-listed counterparts. At the same time if listed companies decide to go for external labour market, they may have advantages over their non-listed counterparts due to public recognition and could have access to a larger pool of potentially suitable candidates. Therefore, it could be assumed that there are differences in staffing practices between listed and non-listed companies and those differences could be inherently linked with listed/non-listed status. For the purpose of the investigation, a non-listed company is defined as a proprietary company, not listed in any recognized stock exchange, whose ordinary shares are closely held.

The investigation of this study deals with staffing practices at the organization level with reference to junior level managerial jobs. A random sample of 200 companies (100 listed and 100 non-listed) was drawn from the list of companies registered under Companies Act of Sri Lanka (No. 17 of 1982). The self-administered questionnaire was chosen as the main mode for data collection. Questionnaires with an accompanying letter were sent to HR managers of 200

companies. If there was no HR manager, the person who involves with personnel matters was requested to complete the questionnaire. As in Harel and Tzafrir' s (1999) study, the questionnaires were sent to HR managers mainly as they have the greatest access to the data related to HRM activities, in particular, staffing. Questionnaires were voluntarily completed and returned by 65 (33 listed and 32 non-listed) of the 200 designated companies within 3 weeks of initial questionnaire distribution. A total of 62 usable responses (31 listed and 31 non-listed) resulted in a 31 per cent response rate. This response rate is considered as reasonable based on norms set for HR related research (Baruch, 1999; Roth and BeVier, 1998). Responded 62 companies were categorised into 8 broad business sectors (12 - Banks, Finance and Insurance, 4 - Beverage, Food and Tobacco, 5 - Chemical and Pharmaceuticals, 8 - Footwear and Textiles, 8 - Information Technology, 12 - Manufacturing, 8 - Transportation and Warehousing, and 5 – Telecommunication).

Data collection instruments and analysis

The self-administered survey questionnaire covered six aspects of staffing as listed below.

- the existence and the utilisation of job analysis information in the staffing process;
- the most frequently utilised internal and external sources of labour in recruitment;
- the qualities and attributes most frequently sought for in selection;
- the most frequently utilised selection methods to assess the possession of qualities and attributes sought for;

- the means by which companies validate the staffing practices, staffing problems faced, how mismatches were identified if there were any, and remedies that have been taken to rectify the identified mismatches in the newly hired employees;
- the extent to which HR managers and line managers involve in the staffing process in HR managers' perception.

The questionnaire item on the “existence of job analysis information” provided a “yes/no” option. The rest of the questionnaire items listed a range of options derived from the review of literature (Heraty and Morley, 1998; Stewart and Knowles, 2000; Tanova, 2003) and invited respondents to tick the most relevant option. Further, a tick box labelled “other” was also added to the list to enable respondents to state any other which were not offered by the questionnaire. The last question of the questionnaire invited respondents to make any other comments in relation to staffing practices in the companies. The questionnaire was piloted with a random sample of 10 companies, which agreed to participate in the survey.

It was decided to supplement self-administered questionnaire survey with interviews to explore staffing practices. The semi-structured interview outline was developed covering all the six main areas of the investigation stated above. Using a small sample of HR managers from ten listed and five non-listed companies, one-to-one semi-structured interview sessions of about one hour duration were conducted to obtain more in-depth and meaningful data. Ten listed companies consisted of companies belong to Banks, Finance and Insurance (4), Beverage, Food and Tobacco (1), Chemical and Pharmaceuticals (1), and Manufacturing (4) sectors while five non-

listed companies consisted of companies belong to Footwear and Textiles (2), Information Technology (1), Transportation and Warehousing (1), and Telecommunication (1) sectors.

In analysing data, in addition to descriptive statistics, chi-square test was used appropriately to investigate the differences in staffing practices between listed and non-listed companies at the significant level of .05. HR managers' comments on staffing practices were categorised and incorporated into the discussion of results along with questionnaire data.

Findings

Usage of information from job analysis in staffing

Results revealed that 40.3 percent (25) of the companies use job analysis information in staffing. Specifically, 41.9 per cent of the listed (13), and 38.7 per cent of the non-listed (12) companies use information from job analysis in staffing. During the interviews, few HR managers from the companies that use job analysis information in staffing mentioned that they send copies of job descriptions and person specifications to potential candidates with official company application form. Few other HR managers mentioned that information from job description is discussed with candidates at the selection interviews while some others revealed that they issue a copy of the job description to new hires after being selected. When searching for candidates possessing multiple criteria, information from job analysis was deemed necessary to short-list and to conduct interviews. Majority of HR managers revealed that if job description and person specification were not available for the vacant position, the relevant heads of departments have to prepare

those with the help of the HR department before commencing recruitment. Thus, none of the HR managers interviewed revealed that they commence staffing activities without any reference to documentation.

Sources of labour

It is perceived that an internal labour market exists to the degree that positions are filled from within the company based on the information from performance evaluation or succession plans. As shown in table 1, 15 companies (24%) use internal labour market as the main method of recruitment when filling managerial level positions. Though all the 15 companies indicated promoting personnel within the function, only 6 companies revealed the existence of cross promotion between functions too. When comparing listed and non-listed companies, non-listed companies have a greater tendency to recruit internally based on internal promotions within the function (29.0%) than do their listed counterparts (19.4%).

Take in Table I

According to some HR managers interviewed, internal labour market as a source of recruitment brings with it a number of distinct advantages. Internal selection reduces the socialization period. Further, it is considered to be a good personnel practice for not only it could be viewed as a positive motivator by current employees but also the quality of the internal labour market is continuously upgraded and maintained through career development and multiskilling. The literature also provide evidence to new hires who entered the organization via internal

recruitment sources experienced less unmet expectations than employees recruited via external recruitment sources (Moser, 2005). However, the survey results of the 62 companies suggest that the companies move away from internal labour market and prefer to recruit from external labour market (62-15= 47 i.e., 76%). The growing internationalisation of organizations and emphasis on effective management team dynamics has increased the necessity for innovative, multi-experienced, and dynamic management. Thus, it is not altogether unexpected that organizations are unwilling to limit themselves to filling management vacancies from within their organizations.

Table II shows a comparison of the most frequently used selection methods based on ranks (the least sum of ranks denotes the highest priority). As shown in Table II, advertising is ranked as the most preferred method of recruitment. Priority given for advertising does not differ by the type of the company- listed or non-listed.

Take in Table II

During the interviews, HR managers revealed that the external recruitment relies upon advertising in national newspapers. Advertisements are precise and well structured to promote a larger pool of potentially suitable candidates to be applied. Some companies make their advertisements more creative to attract a larger pool of more qualified candidates by being able to sell the company's image through advertisements designed for recruitment. Information pertaining to the job and job holder are common to be included in the advertisements. However, in most cases, companies do not specify the exact salary in the advertisements instead indicate a

“high salary with an attractive fringe-benefit package” or “salary is negotiable”. Potential candidates are required to write in accompanied with their CVs on or before the closing date specified in the advertisement.

Job posting is ranked 2nd in the overall sample, 2nd in the listed and 3rd in the non-listed companies. During the interviews it is revealed that for job posting, companies use intranet, e-mail, departmental notice boards and/or internal news bulletins. The interested internal candidates are required to send in their applications through their heads of departments to HR manager. HR managers viewed job posting as a good personnel practice, which gives an opportunity for existing personnel to apply when information from performance evaluations are not used to fill vacancies internally. Further, job posting is also seen as a source for recommendations through existing personnel.

Internal promotions is ranked 3rd in the overall sample, 3rd in the listed and 2nd in the non-listed companies as shown in Table II. During the interviews, few HR managers revealed the existence of skills inventories which are updated every six months. HR managers identify the importance of informing the potential candidates in advance the number of vacancies available to overcome misunderstandings. If proper formal performance evaluation systems or the provision of HRD opportunities to insiders do not exist, such companies are reluctant to use internal labour market even at the junior managerial level. Prevalence of similar situations in the Sri Lankan private sector was also observed by Akuratiyagamage (2005).

Personal recommendation is ranked 4th across all categories. In this study, recruitment agency was not ranked as a highly preferred method though literature reveals the frequent use of recruitment agencies in the private sector across all managerial levels (Heraty and Morley, 1998). Although recruitment agencies are expensive and time consuming, few companies do get their service. An HR manager from a company that use recruitment agencies revealed the importance of sending detailed job profile and candidate profile to the agency to short-list prospective candidates. The agency's choice of short-listed candidates is sent to the company for further screening processes.

According to majority of HR managers interviewed, certain recruitment methods such as personal recommendations act as realistic job previews by providing potential applicants with accurate and detailed information about the organization and the job. Thus, HR managers identified that employees recruited through referrals tends to stay longer and less likely to be terminated. Further, the number of job applicants that can be attracted also varies with the method of recruitment. HR managers identified advertisements as the most powerful in attracting a larger pool of candidates with exact qualities sought for. Few HR managers also revealed that the methods such as job posting and redeployment have to be used as company policies. During the interviews, Sri Lankan HR managers revealed the fact that different external sources reach different applicant populations and that by using different sources companies could attract applicants who differ in their personality, ability, motivation, or some other personal attribute that may impact job performance and attitudes. Thus, companies do not tend to solely rely on single source for recruitment, instead like to draw talent from different sources, wherever appropriate.

Selection criteria

The study was designed to ascertain which particular qualities and attributes are considered to be important in recruitment and selection. In the survey questionnaire, 8 selection criteria used by Stewart and Knowles (2000) were provided along with educational qualifications, previous work experience, and professional qualifications. Further, an option to state any other criteria sought for is also provided. In addition to the list of options provided respondents mentioned personality, self confidence and customer care. As the number of respondents that mentioned these three is considerably larger, those were also included in the analysis. As shown in Figure 1, the strongest emphasis is placed on applicant's educational qualifications. The priority given for educationally qualified candidates does not differ by the type of the company-listed or non listed. Companies also emphasise work experience, professional qualifications and personality, which were rated second, third, and fourth respectively across all categories. When comparing listed and non-listed companies, there were no significant differences between their preference for educational qualifications ($p=.477$, $\text{sig}=.490$), work experience ($p=1.476$, $\text{sig}=.224$), professional qualifications ($p=.272$, $\text{sig}=.602$), and personality ($p=.258$, $\text{sig}=.611$). For the rest of the selection criteria chi square test was not performed due to the small number of companies reported searching for such.

Take in Figure 1

Selection methods

Figure 2 shows selection methods used by the companies. Selection interview rated as the most frequently used method (88.7% total sample, 83.9% listed and 93.5% non-listed). When comparing listed and non-listed companies, there are no significant differences in the usage of interviews ($p=1.449$, $\text{sig}=.229$). Written examination is the second most used method followed by psychometric test and assessment centre across all categories.

Take in Figure 2

During the interviews, HR managers revealed that candidates respond to adverts in news papers by sending detailed bio-data/CVs together with names of two unrelated referees. After the stipulated time period for the applicants to send in their CVs, initial screening and short-listing starts based on job description and job specification. When organizations are receiving increasing numbers of applications per vacancy, pre-selection devices becomes a necessity. In this context, sending company specific standard official application form to short-listed candidates is identified as an advantage to compare and filter high potential candidates. Few companies revealed that they send job information pack to prospective applicants, which includes the job description, person specification, official application form and a brief of company policies on recruitment and selection.

HR managers revealed that they do not solely depend on the information provided by the candidates in their CVs; written examinations are adopted to support the selection process. Such

examinations are designed to ascertain qualities such as applicant's intelligent level, logical thinking, proficiency in languages and general business awareness. Applicants who are successful in the written examination are called for interviews. The majority of companies conduct series of interviews. At each interview stage potential candidates are short-listed for the next interview stage. The first two interview stages are conducted by the line managers with the assistance of HR managers. Few companies revealed that the first interview involve solely the line manager. The third and/or final interview is conducted by a board comprising of three or four senior line managers and the HR manager. Companies use some method of scoring during the interviews when more than one person assesses a candidate. According to one HR manager, a summary of educational and other qualities of candidates extracted from CVs are given to the interview panel and each interviewer rate, separately, interviewee performance during the interview as per the guide matrix developed by the HR division. Based on the average marks scored by each candidate, few candidates are selected for the final round of interviews. After the preliminary interview but before the final interview, references are obtained from previous employers/referees of the short-listed candidates. HR managers identified conducting reference checks and medical examinations as a norm during the selection process. In some companies, only one interview session is held with the involvement of panel of staff members. The majority of HR managers revealed the existence of having a pre-interview discussion session with the interview panel before commencing the panel interviews.

Though costs associated with assessment centres are high, companies reported the use of assessment centres after the first interview but before the final interview. Almost all HR managers revealed having psychometric tests on the same day of the assessment centres. Only

one listed multinational company made reference to the use of Belbin questionnaire to establish team roles. Few companies indicated the use of oral presentations as a part of an assessment centre exercise. Presentations aim to assess qualities such as presentation skills, content, analytical skills, and communication skills.

Validation of staffing practices

With regard to the existence of the validation of staffing practices, 38 companies (61.3%) indicated the use of some form of validation- i.e., 67.8 per cent listed (21), and 54.8 per cent of non-listed (17) companies. Table III shows in detail the avenues in which HR managers get information of mismatches in the newly hired employees.

Take in Table III.

From Table III, it could be seen that 68 per cent of the total sample, 81 per cent of the listed, and 55 per cent of the non-listed companies mainly rely on line managers to point out whether selections are correct. The focus here is on matching the capabilities and inclinations of new hires against the demands inherent in a given job. Only four companies in the sample conduct exit interviews. In some companies no performance evaluations are held at the end of the probation period. Thus, new hires eventually get confirmed in the relevant department after the completion of probation period. Few HR managers attributed many hiring problems to over reliance on interviews. An HR manager from a listed company revealed the practice of calculating new hire success rate. The majority of HR managers who revealed the existence of

some form of validation further acknowledged the absence of formal systems within the context of staffing and identified it as a potential problem.

Table III also shows the actions taken if and when mismatches were identified. The extension of probationary period (24.2% total sample, 22.6% listed, and 25.8% non-listed), and a provision of necessary training (21.0% total sample, 19.4% listed, and 22.6% non-listed) are commonly used. Many HR managers reported that new hires resigned when they found that they were in the wrong jobs (24.2% total sample, 29.0% listed, and 19.4% non-listed). In this context, Anderson *et al.*, (2001), Bauer et al (2001) and Bauer et al (1998) revealed the importance of investigating perceptions of new hires on staffing practices.

Involvement of HR and line managers in staffing

Results revealed that 92 per cent of the companies (all the listed and 84% non-listed) have separate HR departments/units. Thus, chi square test does not reveal any significant differences between listed and non-listed companies at the significant level of .05 ($p=3.153$, sig.=.076).

Figure 3 shows the results for the existence of HR department and HR/line managers' involvement in staffing. As shown in Figure 3, staffing activities are completed through a combination of HR and line management involvement (46.7%+19.4% = 66.1%) rather than having sole responsibility. This indicates a trend to delegate staffing activity to individual departments with staffing needs. This phenomenon was also observed by Heraty and Morley (1998) and Zhu and Dowling (2002). As shown in Figure 3, 47 per cent of HR managers

indicated that staffing activities are completed through HR department in consultation with line management while 20 per cent of the HR managers indicated that staffing activities are completed through line management in consultation with the HR department. Further, it is apparent that a larger proportion of listed companies reported line management involvement in staffing ($61.3\%+16.2\%=77.2\%$) than non-listed companies ($32.2\%+22.5\%=54.7\%$). During the interviews, it was revealed that line managers are more involved in the areas of final hiring decisions and also in HR planning at the departmental level while HR managers are more involved in staffing related policy making, recruiting candidates, and for early screening processes. Only 25.8 per cent of respondents (16) indicated HR management is solely responsible for staffing activities and there is no devolvement to line managers. However, only 5 non-listed companies indicated that line management is solely responsible for staffing activities and they do not have HR departments/units or specialised HR personnel in the companies. Thus, no company with a HR department/unit reported complete devolvement of staffing activities to line managers.

Take in Figure 2

HR managers from subsidiaries of multinational corporations revealed that many HR related policies are determined at the level of the establishment. However, when it comes to workforce adjustment, it is more likely to be decided at the international headquarter level. If so, the trend of devolvement of staffing practices to host country (Sri Lanka) managers and they become the owners are not supported. In this connection, Heraty and Morley (1998) also found that international headquarter level is reclaiming more strategic policy decisions compared to early

1990s. At the host country level, however, responsibilities for staffing decisions are shared jointly by HR function and line management.

Conclusions and managerial implications

The research investigated staffing practices in relation to junior level management positions in the Sri Lankan private sector based on the assumption that there may be significant differences between listed and non-listed companies. One of the main differences between listed and non-listed companies were the preference shown by non-listed companies to recruit internally based on internal promotions than do their listed counterparts. This is somewhat unexpected as listed companies, by virtue of their reputation as listed in the stock market, could be expected to maintain series of career ladders for their personnel. When considering the methods of recruitment, priority given for advertising as the main method does not differ by the type of the company- listed or non-listed. When comparing listed and non-listed companies in terms of selection criteria, there were no significant differences between their preference for educational qualifications, work experience, and professional qualifications, which were rated as first, second, and third respectively. Further, when comparing listed and non-listed companies in terms of selection methods, selection interview rated as the most frequently used method followed by written examination, psychometric test and assessment centre by both listed and non-listed companies. Furthermore, results also revealed that if mismatches in the newly hired employees were identified, both listed and non-listed companies extend the probationary period and provide necessary training. Thus, though it was expected to find significant differences between listed

and non-listed companies in their staffing practices, the findings led to reveal more similar staffing practices.

Overall, the results of the study suggest that the companies move away from internal labour market and prefer to recruit from external labour market. This has implications for practice as internal recruitment not only motivate current employees to perform better and increase their commitment towards the organization, but may also help to create a flexible/mobile internal labour market whose job security could be improved through upward or lateral career opportunities. Thus, greater preference for external labour market may not represent a deliberate, organization-wide, strategic selection strategy.

Sri Lankan companies draw talent from different sources. Each source of recruitment brings with it a number of distinct advantages and disadvantages. Different sources of recruitment reach different applicant populations and attract applicants who differ in qualities and attributes that may impact job performance and attitudes. However, this may lead to high level of investment in recruitment and selection. And also implies the need of objective selection criteria and sophisticated selection methods.

High preference for educational and professional qualifications implies that organizations surveyed are looking for qualified candidates. The preference for previous work experience indicates that companies identify work experience as one of the requirements in the career transition into a junior managerial role. In Sri Lanka, on one hand, increasing number of educated youth enter into the labour market annually and unemployment indicates an increasing

trend with the increase in the level of education. On the other hand, the economic condition of the country suggests the possibilities of attracting FDI into the country. For investors, local market, regional market and future market possibilities provide motivating force to invest. The quality of labour was one of the factors that attract investments to Sri Lanka. This implies the need of creating accurate opportunity awareness among job seekers. Thus, a practical implication for higher education institutions and job seekers is to focus on the expectations and requirements of the organizations. Another situation that emerges in this connection is the trend of Sri Lankan organizations receiving a greater volume of applications for job vacancies. Organizations therefore have to plan their recruitment activities and also to use more sophisticated selection methods. This also has several implications. The usage of more sophisticated selection methods could be quite costly if organizations do not have trained staff and require the help of professional psychologists from outside the organization to administer and interpret test results. However, the misuse of such instruments may be even costly to the organization and may also be demoralising to the new hire who may find him/herself in the wrong job. This could demotivate the new hire as well as the rest of the staff.

Findings revealed that the Sri Lankan companies highly rely on interviews as a selection method. Many of the inherent problems of interviewing may be reduced due to the use of panel interviews and a number of stages in the selection process. However, interview decisions would be inappropriate without complementary staffing practices such as training of interviewers, consistency in interview evaluations, common grading system in defining personal attributes and the evaluation of interview outcomes on the basis of job performance. Hence, the use of personal

interviews in Sri Lankan organizations needs to be developed along with other related HR practices.

Despite the apparent confidence that some companies demonstrated regarding employee retention, company experiences showed that instances of new hires leaving due to mismatches do exist. HR specialists in Sri Lanka may need to realize the importance of the formation of expectations during the staffing process. This implies the need of the provision of extensive information during organization socialization to facilitate acquisition of the organization's cultural perspective that in turn reduce the anxiety and uncertainty attendant to new surroundings and new responsibilities. This further implies the need of further investigations into perceptions of new hires/job applicants on staffing practices such as, reactions to selection methods and their decision-making in the selection process.

Results did not reveal complete devolvement of staffing activities to line managers and HR managers still retain responsibility and accountability for the overall success of staffing. The combination of line manager and HR manager involvement may minimize the risk of failure. On the other hand, the devolvement may provide more discretionary time for HR managers to concentrate in creating coherent and consistent staffing practices with organizational business strategies and with other associated functions of HRM such as HR planning, and training and development. This implies that in the free labour market staffing can no longer be conducted just as an administrative task. This study also suggests that HR managers need to acquire professional skills of managing human resources.

Limitations and future research

This study was confined to exploring staffing practices in the private sector in Sri Lanka and comparing the practices by listed and non-listed companies. Future studies could be extended to cross-industry and cross-national comparisons as managerial preferences in staffing policy areas, like other HRM policy areas, could reflect underlying managerial values associated with industry concerned or with country of origin of the organization. Further, while finding general tendencies are useful, there is a need for an analysis of relationships between staffing practices and desired HR/organizational outcomes.

Another limitation of the study was that sample consisted only of HR managers and the study relied on self-reports for data gathering. Bartlett *et al.*, (2002) argued that the self-report measures from HR managers may not reflect accurately the attitudes towards management practices of the organization. Thus, study sample could be extended to collect data beyond the perception of HR managers to include multiple sources such as line managers and newly hired employees as future research.

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Tables

Table I: Internal recruitment based on performance evaluation

Item	Total sample		Listed		Non-listed	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Internal promotion within the function	15	24.2	6	19.4	9	29.0
Cross promotion between functions	6	9.7	3	9.7	3	9.7

Table II: Recruitment methods

Source	Total sample	Listed	Non-listed
Advertising	1	1	1
Job posting	2	2	3
Internal promotions based on performance evaluation	3	3	2
Personal recommendation	4	4	4
Career guidance/Professional institutions	5	6	5
Walk-in	6	5	6
Redeployment	7	7	8
Recruitment agency	8	8	7

Table III: Identification of mismatches and actions taken

Item	Total sample		Listed		Non-listed	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
How mismatches were identified						
Immediate superior identify during day-to-day work	16	25.8	9	29.0	7	22.6
Immediate superior identify during formal performance evaluation	26	42.0	16	52.0	10	32.3
During exit interviews conducted by HR department	4	6.5	3	9.7	1	3.2
Actions taken if mismatches were identified						
Probationary period extended	15	24.2	7	22.6	8	25.8
Provide training	13	21.0	6	19.4	7	22.6
Candidate is transferred to a suitable department	8	13.0	2	6.5	6	19.4
Increments being withheld	1	1.6	1	3.2	0	00.0
Candidate resigned	15	24.2	9	29.0	6	19.4
Terminated by the company	7	11.3	3	9.7	4	12.9

Figures

Figure 1: Selection criteria

Figure 2: Selection methods

Figure 3: Responsibility for staffing

